

5G Millimeter Wave

By Edwin Amuga

Abstract

Many countries are increasingly announcing deployment of the 5G wireless communication in a range of areas of application. A considerable number of academic institutions and industries have also initiated intense research and face the challenges faced by the 6G. This paper aims to review the wireless generation and millimeter wave application advancement in the face of 5G. Millimeter wave applications are crucial in 5G communication and has a great application opportunity in upcoming 6G communication. Conversely, it can still be improved for use in radio and network application to form new applications. The paper specifically bases on millimeter wave technology and approaches its advantages and disadvantages and its application in different millimeter wave bands. The paper focuses on radar systems, radiometry, satellite imagery, radio communication, and atmospheric sensing.

Problem statement

Today's mobile users demand faster speeds of data and increased service reliability. The 5G network, as the next frontier, promises to satisfy this demand among others. The 5G aims to handle more traffic at higher speeds as compared to the base stations making up today's cellular networks. In pursuit of this, brand new technologies suites are being designed to deliver data at a speed of 20 GB per second as compared to 1GB per second on 4G networks. The technologies to support 5G include small cells, full duplex, millimeter waves, massive MIMO and beam forming. The main problem faced by wireless networks today is that more device users are consuming more data than before but are crammed on the same radio-frequency spectrum bands

used by mobile providers. This implies that every device user has less bandwidth thereby resulting in slower service and increased number of dropped connections.

The wireless communication fifth generation network is a network for broad band cellular networks with support features aimed at feeding data intensive application demands including the millimeter wave frequencies, beam forming, huge antenna arrays and dense cells among other features. It is the planned successor of the 4G network which, for the better part of the decade, has been providing connectivity to the latest smart phones. The 5G network is no different from its predecessors as the service area is divided into small geographical areas referred to as cells. All devices in each cell are connected to telephone network and the internet through a local cell antenna using radio waves. One of the most notable advantages that come with 5G is the fact that it has a greater bandwidth, thereby giving higher speeds of download of up to 10 gigabits a second. The wider bandwidth is also expected to be utilized for general internet service providers for desktop computers and laptops, offering a tight competition for Internet service providers such as cable internet. The 5G network will also enable the use of new applications in the IoT and machine learning areas. The high speed offered by 5G is achieved using radio waves of higher frequency that its predecessors lack. Conversely, higher frequency radio waves do not have longer useful physical range which implies that smaller geographic cells will be used.

With beam forming, the fifth generation wireless networks need more base stations and four times less power to provide capacity to users and same coverage performances as compared to the fourth generation reference network. The 5G network is also three times more energy efficient as compared to the 4G network. The hybrid beam forming architecture is more suitable and should be considered when designing 5G cellular network. This paper investigates the beam

forming techniques using a range of architectures and attempts to evaluate 5G wireless access network performance using tool for deployment of capacity-based network.

The evolution of standards of telecommunication is driven by the increase in demand for applications with higher latency and throughput. The fifth generation network and others to come will have telecommunication standards to accommodate larger wireless connection number to support existing and evolving application such as HD streaming, real-time gaming, social media, full featured web browsing. 5G features such as the Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO), small dense networks, beam forming, millimeter wave frequency and movable base stations. The continued growth of volume of data traffic and remarkable network infrastructure expansion is expected to drive an increase in consumption of energy in wireless networks. This will result in increased greenhouse gas emission and will pose environmental protection urgency.

There has been a growing academia and industry research interest aimed at resolving unprecedented technical challenges and requirements on next generation 5G wireless systems. There are more than 5 billion devices that are expected to make use of wireless connections that run data and voice applications among others in today's networks. This demand for more capacity remains a key driver for mobile network evolution to 5G. For a smooth working of data-intensive applications, the research recommends the following technical requirements for yet to be standardized 5G.

Recommendations

The 5G network should be maintained at a minimum of 1Gigabit per second connectivity anytime and anywhere in terms of coverage and data rate. Latency remains a hard requirement to achieve as data needs to be delivered to a destination within a given time period. The end-to-end

latency requirement for 5G network should be maintained between 1 and 5 ms. In terms of the number of connected devices, the 5G network should also be used to connect a huge number of devices, up to 100 times the 4G wireless network data rate. In terms of multiple radio access technologies, the 5G network will be built upon the existing wireless network technologies, such as the long term evolution (LTE), Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM), 3G, high speed packet access (HSPA), wireless fidelity (wifi) and long term evolution advanced (LTE-A) rather than replacing them (Huang, Liu, Wang, Sun and Xiao, 2018). The 5G wireless network should be tailored to meet data consuming application requirements in terms of energy and cost efficiency but at lower cost and higher energy efficiency in comparison with wireless networks in existence.

With these requirements, there will be a range of new technologies enabled to support 5G network. The millimeter wave frequency will be most suitable to respond to huge network capacity and gigabit broadband application with the use of frequency spectrum under 6GHz.

To sort out the problem of low bandwidth, slower service and dropped connections for mobile users, a range of measures should be utilized. One of the measures include transmitting signals on a whole new spectrum swath that has not been used before in mobile service. The broad casting of millimeter waves is being experimented for this as they use higher frequencies than that used by radio waves used for mobile phones.

Millimeter waves are broadcast between 30 and 300 gigahertz frequency compared to bands below 6GHz used in past mobile devices. The name millimeter waves is derived from the fact that their lengths vary between 1 and 10mm as compared to radio waves serving today's smart phones measuring tens of centimeters length. Satellite and radar system operators used

millimeter waves to real world applications in the past. A number of cellular providers are also adopting their use in sending data between stationary points as in two base stations. The use of millimeter waves in connecting users is, however, a new approach.

The use of millimeter waves has one main drawback, in that, they cannot easily travel through obstacles and buildings and can also be absorbed by rain or foliage. This is why the 5G network will most likely be used to complement traditional cellular towers with the new small cell technology. Wireless network reliable for smart phone use, VR games and autonomous cars is expected to be built with Millimeter waves and other 5G technologies. Companies and researchers have set high hopes based on the promises held by 5G such as the ultra low latency and record breaking speeds of data for users. If the remaining challenges can be confronted and solved, and all the systems made to work together, consumers will start enjoying ultrafast 5G network services in the next five years.

The 5G will also be supported by the use of Massive MIMO technology, which is in itself an extension of the 4G technology to larger antennas. A big number of antenna arrays are combined to provide the ability to make use of maximum possible freedom degrees available in spatial domains. It is, therefore, possible to focus the energies towards a particular direction while preventing propagation in the wrong direction, a practice known as beam forming. The millimeter wave frequency is used to achieve this as this higher carrier frequency needs elements of an antenna to be very small to allow the use of many antennas at the mobile station and at the base station. Beam forming architectures are of three types, which are widely researched. These are radio and analog frequency beam forming, digital beam forming and hybrid beam forming architectures.

Digital beam forming architecture assumes that a transceiver is behind each antenna, and for that, the processing of the entire array is performed at the baseband side. In analog beam forming, MIMO control and beam forming is done at radio frequency level. The transceiver drives the antenna array and the processing of the receive and transmit array is done using RF components with phase shifting and potential capabilities of gain adjustment. In hybrid beam forming, MIMO control and beam forming is divided between baseband and radio frequencies. Each of the antenna element sets is driven by a transceiver. The hybrid architecture, on the other hand, is able to use two to eight transceivers.

Small cell technology, which is also used to support 5G will work to satisfy the increasing traffic demands emanating from an increase in the growth of user number, as infrastructure densification will be introduced to accommodate 5G cells in the 4G macro cell network as a priority aspect in communication on the 5G platform.

There is also ongoing research to extend the useful range of millimeter-wave 5G transmissions beyond the perceived limits from less than 1.6km to 5 kilometers. This has been approached by first addressing the problem of loss of power suffered by signals over distance due to the fact that rain disperses them and are also absorbed by water vapor and oxygen molecules (Shen, Liu, Zhao, Huang, Shi and Huang, 2019). The waves cannot also go through solid objects and buildings. Due to this, the millimeter waves can only carry a huge data amount but only over short distance as compared to longer wavelengths. Conversely, the short propagation range allows the reuse distance of smaller frequencies. The short wavelength allows medium sized antennas to have small width of beams and therefore an increased potential for frequency reuse. Millimeter waves have been used for military fire control, short range wireless networks, airport security scanners and scientific research. The lowest frequency ranges are used

as a major new application in the newest generation of cell phone networks. Research has shown that the use of upgraded software for the existing carrier-grade 5G radio hardware helps make possible the longer distance transmission.

Propagation

Millimeter waves are propagated by line-of-sight paths. This is because they are not reflected by the ionosphere as do not travel along the earth as ground waves as seen in lower radio wave frequencies. The millimeter waves suffer attenuation as they pass through foliage and blocked by building at typical power densities. The absorption by atmospheric gases remains a huge factor all over the band and increased with frequency. The wavelengths are the same size order as raindrops, enabling precipitation to cause additional attenuation as a result of scattering and absorption. The high loss in free space and absorption in the atmosphere limits useful propagation to only a few kilometers. This means that the waves are useful for densely packed communication network including personal area networks that improve the utilization of the spectrum through reuse of the frequencies.

Millimeter waves exhibit features of optical propagation and can be reflected and focused by small metal surfaces and dielectric lenses between 5 and 30 centimeters diameter. The geometric optics techniques can be utilized due to the fact that the wavelengths are much smaller than equipment manipulating them. The rate of diffraction is relatively lower than in lower frequencies, even though edges of buildings can diffract them. The diffuse reflection is increased due to the fact that surfaces appear rougher. Indoor walls and surfaces cause reflection resulting in serious fading. Doppler frequency shifts is still significant even at pedestrian speeds. Shadowing by the human body is also a problem in the case of portable devices. The waves are

used in airport security millimeter wave scanners since they are able to penetrate clothing and have small wavelengths.

References

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